

Fluoberyllic Acid

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Free fluoberyllic acid has been isolated with the help of cation-exchange resin, Amberlite IR-120 (H-form). Its properties have been studied along with the measurement of its pH and conductance.

Although fluoberyllates, prepared by Ray¹, have been found to be analogous to the corresponding sulphates, but fluoberyllic acid, analogous to sulphuric acid, has not yet been obtained in the free state. Ray² prepared tetramethylammonium hydrofluoberyllate; Ray and Ghosh³ prepared $H_2BeF_4 \cdot Cr_2(BeF_4)_3 \cdot 24 H_2O$. Dutta⁴ from thermometric studies of the system $(NH_4)_2BeF_4-HCl-H_2O$ came to the conclusion that acid salts $3(NH_4)_2BeF_4 \cdot H_2BeF_4$ and $(NH_4)_2BeF_4 \cdot H_2BeF_4$ were formed in solution. Sengupta⁵ from thermometric titration curve, obtained by titrating hydrofluoric acid with beryllium fluoride solution, concluded the formation of H_2BeF_4 in solution. It is therefore reasonable to conclude that fluoberyllic acid does exist in solution.

In the present investigation isolation of a free fluoberyllic acid with the help of cation-exchange resins has been described.

EXPERIMENTAL

Preparation of the Acid.—Ammonium fluoberyllate was obtained by the interaction of calculated amounts of ammonium bifuoride and beryllium carbonate. The solution was evaporated and the salt deposited was recrystallised several times. Purity was checked by chemical analysis.

An approximately $N/2$ solution of ammonium fluoberyllate was passed through a cation-exchange resin column of Amberlite I.R. 120 (100-200 mesh) H^+ form (1.4×30 cm) in a polythene tube, drawn out at the lower end and closed with a screw clip. The fluoberyllate solution was passed through the resin bed at a flow rate of 1 ml/min. The effluent was collected in a polythene bottle. The acid was found to be free of ammonium ion (tested with Nessler's solution).

The acid (5 ml) on analysis provided the following results. (Found: H, 0.00634 g.; Be, 0.0279 g.; F, 0.2374 g. H : Be : F requires 2.04 : 1 : 4.03).

1. *Z. anorg. allgm. Chem.*, 1931, **201**, 209.
2. *Ibid.*, 1931, **201**, 300.
3. *Ibid.*, 1959, **300**, 102.
4. *Science & Culture*, 1953, **18**, 599.
5. *This *Journal*, 1960, **37**, 291.

Method of Analysis.—The acid in 5 ml of the prepared solution was estimated by titration with a standard NaOH solution and total hydrogen was calculated.

Beryllium was estimated by precipitation as $\text{Be}(\text{OH})_2$ and igniting it to BeO . For estimating fluorine, beryllium was precipitated as $\text{Be}(\text{OH})_2$ with ammonia and removed by filtration. In the filtrate fluorine was estimated by precipitation as CaF_2 in ammoniacal medium and weighing as CaF_2 after ignition. Fluorine was also estimated by titration with a standard thorium nitrate solution with Alizarin S as indicator.

Potentiometric Titration

pH titrations were carried out in a Cambridge pH-meter, calibrated at pH 4, using quinhydrone as electrode. The acid was titrated with a standard NaOH solution. The results are recorded in Table I.

TABLE I

Conc. alkali = 0.95*N* - NaOH. Conc. of H_2BeF_4 = 1.5*N*. Vol. of H_2BeF_4 taken = 5 ml.

Alkali added.	pH.	$d\text{pH}/dV$.	Alkali added.	pH.	$d\text{pH}/dV$.
0.0 ml	1.20	..	3.8 ml	4.68	1.15
1.0	1.52	0.32	4.5	5.37	0.98
2.0	2.03	0.51	5.0	5.74	0.74
2.5	2.59	1.12	6.0	6.13	0.39
3.0	3.40	1.62	6.5	6.38	0.50
3.2	3.78	1.90	6.7	6.43	0.75
3.6	4.45	1.67	7.1	8.76	5.80

Conductometric Titration

Titration were carried out in a dipping type conductometric cell, the glass surface of which was coated with a layer of paraffin, before platinising. The acid was taken in a polythene vessel. The conductance was measured at 25° (Table II).

TABLE II

H_2BeF_4 taken = 2 ml. Conc. of H_2BeF_4 = 1.267*N*. Conc. alkali = 1.5 *N* - NaOH.

Alkali added.	Resistance <i>R</i> .	1/ <i>R</i> .	Alkali added.	Resistance <i>R</i> .	1/ <i>R</i> .
0.08 ml	0.86×10^2 ohm	0.01163×10^{-1}	0.96 ml	1.8×10^2 ohm	0.0555×10^{-1}
0.16	0.92	0.01087	1.04	1.7	0.0588
0.24	1.0	0.1000	1.12	1.6	0.0625
0.32	1.2	0.0833	1.20	1.4	0.0714
0.48	1.3	0.0769	1.28	1.3	0.0769
0.56	1.4	0.0714	1.36	1.2	0.0833
0.72	1.5	0.0666	1.44	1.1	0.0909
0.80	1.6	0.0625	1.52	1.0	0.1000
0.88	1.7	0.058	1.60	1.0	..

DISCUSSION

The solution obtained by passing ammonium fluoberyllate through the resin column contains the complex acid H_2BeF_4 . Fluoberyllic acid is fairly stable in solution in the cold.

The acid with $Ba(NO_3)_2$ solution in the cold formed a white precipitate, insoluble in mineral acids. Analysis of the precipitate corresponds with the formula $BaBeF_4$. (Found: Ba, 61.75. Calc. 61.77%). X-ray analysis of the substance along with a sample of $BaSO_4$ prepared under identical conditions, confirmed their isomorphism.

Fluoberyllic acid with copper carbonate formed a blue solution which on crystallisation afforded blue crystals, isomorphous with copper sulphate, as shown by overgrowths on copper sulphate crystals. The crystals on analysis corresponded to the formula $CuBeF_4 \cdot 5H_2O$. (Found: Cu, 26.53. Calc. 26.63%).

From the reactions with barium nitrate and also with copper carbonate, it was definitely proved that the solution, obtained by passing ammonium fluoberyllate through the resin column, contained fluoberyllic acid and it was not beryllium fluoride, as in the latter case barium fluoride and copper fluoride would have been precipitated.

Feigl and Chaeffer⁶ have pointed out that BeF_4^{2-} is such a stable complex that beryllium nitrate solution is able to dissolve insoluble fluorides and demask reaction systems, which are masked by fluorides, producing in all cases a stable fluoberyllate. AlF_6^{3-} ions respond to tests for Al^{3+} ions in presence of Be^{2+} ions, showing greater stability of BeF_4^{2-} complex in comparison with AlF_6^{3-} .

According to the observation of Dutta and Sengupta⁷, the fluoberyllate ion is highly stable, particularly in solution with *pH* lower than 5 and they utilised this property of the BeF_4^{2-} ion in the qualitative estimation of Be as $BaBeF_4$.

FIG. 1

Conductometric titrations of fluoberyllic acid with NaOH reveals two inflections in the curve (Fig. 2).

6. *Anal. Chem.*, 1951, **23**, 351.

7. *This Journal*, 1956, **33**, 146.

FIG. 2

This proves that fluoberylic acid is dibasic, the inflection points corresponding to the formation of HBeF_4^- and BeF_4^{2-} ions respectively. *pH* titrations with NaOH also reveals two sharp breaks leading to the same conclusion (Fig. 1).

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